

Theory of Special relativity with Quantum Properties

Abstract:

The speed of light is a constant in the universe. Using this as a background, the theory of relativity is established to show that space and time are relative. However, ~~nothing~~ nothing exists to prove why the speed of light is a constant. The purpose of this paper is to show that the speed of light is a constant in our universe because of Quantum effects. That is, because it does not exist without us measuring it, and it cannot exist for two observers simultaneously. This is done by creating a thought experiment consisting of two observers that have to agree on a constant speed inside ~~for~~ a space and time that is relative.

Structure of the experiment

(1)

Imagine a really long train ~~track~~ of infinite length. Infinite is chosen in this scenario because it helps prevent us from creating a reference frame for this train. Inside this train there are two women. Both women are seated face to face at some arbitrary distance of course that we cannot determine initially. If such a scenario is difficult to comprehend, the picture below serves as a visual aid.

Henceforth we will define both women as Woman 1 and Woman 2 as depicted in the picture above. To complete the picture let us assume that although both observers (Woman 1 and 2) are in the train at an unknown distance, they are both aware that the other

Initial reference frame.

Using the scenario depicted, there are some axioms that we can establish. The first is that both observers will not agree on position. For example, what observer one defines as his right will be depicted by observer two as his left. So both observers using their position as their initial frame of reference will be unable to reconcile where events occur.

Another axiom that can be quickly established is that both observers, using their respective positions as initial frames of reference can disagree on the moments that events occur. For example, if both of them ~~are~~ entered the train at the same moment, and as soon as they were inside the train, they were given a stopwatch that started ticking as soon as "both" and "both" is emphasized here are at their positions, not before and also not if one was at their position and the other is not.

Speed of events

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Using the established scenario created as well as the axioms created, we can ~~agree on~~ ^{create} a third axiom. That is that both observers will be unable to agree on the speed, velocity of an object if they both see the object at the same time. For example, if some event occurs in an arbitrary position in between them, say an object starts to move, they will be unable to agree on the speed of the object. This axiom is better explained using an illustration.

If object 3 starts moving towards observer 2 at a constant speed, both observers will be able to agree on the absolute distance covered by the object, but they will be unable to agree on how long the event will have happened if the event started at their individual locations and had moved towards the arbitrary position described.

(4)

That is, if the only reference point available to them are themselves. This holds true for any object that moves at any location in between both ~~of~~ women. ✱

Implications of the Observations

Let us create an addition to our scenario. Let us assume that both observers are aware of the speed of light as a constant before they got into the infinite train. Let us also say that they are ~~unaware~~ of ~~any other thing related to~~ the event, and they only witness the unaware of any other thing related to the event, and they only witness the event simultaneously, then as stated above, they would be unable to agree on the speed of the object, even using light or rather the speed of light as a reference. This is because observer ~~one~~ will say that the obj if we assume that the object moving is a photon of light, both observers will still disagree on the time it took for the object to have gotten to that position

from their reference point, hence they would continue to disagree on the speed of the photon. This only works if they are unable to know where the photon originated from.

Speed of light as a Quantum effect

If the above axioms prove true, then ~~we~~ further axioms can be made. That is, both observers will be unable to agree on the speed of the photon except they both agree that the photon did not exist until they saw it, and that the photon's existence is completely local and it couldn't have existed until it existed within their individual frames of reference.

Just as before, we shall use a diagram to illustrate this axiom. Assuming that the photon that occurred at point 3 previously, happens to occur at point 3, but this time, both observers

Simultaneously see the same photon as occurring from both their positions. Even if both observers will disagree on the ~~space~~ position of the photon they will agree on the speed of the photon because for each of them, the time it took for the photon to get to that position is different. So woman 1 might say let us use an illustration to depict the effect of location to both observers (woman 1 and 2).

I say it pass by me first, that is I saw it start from my position.

Observer 2 would say I saw event 3 but it started from my position 2 before it got to 3

Simple Harmonic Motion

(7)

~~Let~~ God does not roll dice, as Einstein says, so we can not believe that the speed of light is a constant because we have simultaneously ~~not~~ not observed an event, that is the speed of light is relevant only if it first occurs from our frame of reference. So, ~~we have to offer~~ a counter solution must be offered.

If both observers are undergoing, simple harmonic motion, that is if both observers are moving in a circle, which is ~~basically~~ good for our representation because an infinite circle is a line, and so our infinite train, which is a line could be a circle because it is infinite in another dimension, or in another way of thinking. If both women are moving in a circle (SHM) and all events occur at the center (photon), then regardless of the fact that our spaces are relative and times are relative, because we are undergoing simple harmonic motion (SHM), we can agree on the fact that the speed of light is a constant if ~~it is~~ ^{the} the origin of the photon is at